

TanSat/ACGS Quality Assessment Summary

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AMENDMENT RECORD SHEET

The Amendment Record Sheet below records the history and issue status of this document.

ISSUE	DATE	REASON
1.0 draft	18/11/2021	First Issue DRAFT
2.0	08/09/2022	Addressing ESA comments

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1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Carbon Dioxide Monitoring Scientific Experimental Satellite (TanSat) was China's first dedicated greenhouse gas monitoring mission. Launched on 22nd December 2016, TanSat was tasked with measuring the CO₂ concentration in the Earth's atmosphere across the globe. Equipped with the Atmospheric Carbon dioxide Grating Spectrometer (ACGS), TanSat performed nadir and glint observations of the Earth's surface, recording the spectral signature of reflected sunlight in three different wavebands: the O₂A band (0.76 μm), the weak CO₂ band (1.61 μm), and the strong CO₂ band (2.06 μm). Combined with a priori information, this data is used by retrieval algorithms to infer the total CO₂ column along the line of sight. This is then converted into a dry-air column averaged mole fraction (XCO₂).

1.1 Introduction to the study

The focus of EDAP has been to evaluate the quality and reliability of remote sensing data from satellites to inform decisions relating to the suitability of candidate missions being considered for the Earthnet Third Party Missions (TPM). One part of this has been to assess the quality of data from TanSat as processed by two retrieval algorithms, namely UoL-FP (Bösch et al. 2006), and IAPCAS (Yang et al., 2015). To that end, three objectives were created to meet this goal:

1. Continued comparisons over Total Carbon Column Observing Network (TCCON; Wunch et al., 2011) sites, e.g. include spectral fits.
2. Global (land-only) intercomparisons of XCO₂ retrievals between IAPCAS and CAMS model.
3. Global (land-only) intercomparisons of XCO₂ retrievals between IAPCAS and UoL-FP.

As the study progressed, a fourth objective was added:

4. Global (land-only) intercomparisons of XCO₂ retrievals between UoL-FP and CAMS model.

The study presented in EDAP.REP.21 focused primarily on Objective 1, detailing the methodology behind the UoL-FP/IAPCAS retrievals and providing comparisons between TanSat UoL-FP/IAPCAS retrievals to TCCON. This work, in addition to presenting a comparison with TCCON data, is also focused on Objectives 2, 3, and 4 comparing global, land-based XCO₂ retrievals from UoL-FP to that of IAPCAS, between retrievals from IAPCAS to model XCO₂ values from CAMS, and between retrievals from UoL-FP to model XCO₂ values from CAMS. The work in this study is also coincident with another project by the European Space Agency (ESA) called the Climate Change Initiative + (CCI+). While the data spans a total of 416 days from March 2017 to May 2018, we present results for nine months of this spanning March 2017 to November 2017. It is anticipated that a publication will be written in the near future analysing the entire dataset.

Regarding the Objective 1, data assessment of TanSat Level 2 products of XCO₂ and solar-induced fluorescence (SIF) are presented. The SIF product is TanSat Level 2 v1.0 SIF. The XCO₂ assessment was primarily carried out through comparisons to the total column retrievals from ground-based Fourier Transform Spectrometers (FTS) in the TCCON. In the comparisons, the overpass (or daily mean) bias, scatter, growth rate and seasonal cycle amplitude were evaluated globally. In addition, particular attention has here been devoted to satellite data evaluation at high latitudes which pose challenges for greenhouse gas satellite retrievals. These activities include: 1) data assessment over snow, 2) evaluation of prior atmospheric profiles of CO₂ in the TanSat OCFP retrievals and in the ground-based TCCON GGG2014 retrieval against the AirCore profile measurements at Sodankylä, in Northern Finland, and 3) an initial evaluation of the TanSat Level 2 SIF product in Northern Finland as an example of the product's high-latitude performance.

Biases calculated with the comparison to the TCCON measurements were between -1.6 ppm–1.4 ppm and standard deviations below 2.5 ppm with no noticeable geographical dependence. The growth rate cannot be reliably disentangled from the seasonal variability due to the limited length of the co-located time series. The XCO₂ seasonal cycle amplitude for TanSat does not generally agree with the TCCON although this is likely due to the short time series.

TanSat mission does provide retrievals over snow, albeit their amount is not large and the retrieval errors are systematically higher compared to observations over snow-free landscape. TanSat prior

profile shapes are in good agreement with the AirCore measurements. An initial comparison of the TanSat Level 2 SIF v1.0 and Sentinel-5P TROPOMI TROPOSIF v2.0 SIF products was carried out in Northern Finland. The two products are in good agreement on the timing of the peak photosynthesis and end-of-season with the TROPOSIF.

Regarding Objective 3, both algorithms perform well, and produce similar results to each other. Comparisons of global monthly median maps of XCO₂ show significant differences of 1-4 ppm exist between UoL-FP and IAPCAS retrievals at tropical latitudes (0-20°N) where TCCON validation stations are not available, indicating differences in the bias correction. This is also seen in latitudinal-average plots of XCO₂, as well as in seasonal mean global maps of XCO₂ for UoL-FP and IAPCAS. Both algorithms produce seasonal cycles that closely follow those produced by retrievals from GOSAT and OCO-2 globally. Isolating XCO₂ retrievals to Giorgi regions, we also find that UoL-FP and IAPCAS retrievals closely follow the GOSAT and OCO-2 retrievals.

Comparison, requested by Objective 2 and 4, between monthly median maps of IAPCAS and UoL-FP XCO₂ values to those predicted in CAMS, model ft18r1 shows generally good agreement between the two datasets, with XCO₂ differences of -0.03 ppm on average with a spread of 1.5-1.7 ppm. This spread is similar to that observed when comparing UoL-FP retrievals to those from IAPCAS, indicating agreement to within the precision of the algorithm used. From the model comparisons, evidence of a seasonal bias is seen in the UoL-FP data with respect to the model, while evidence of a latitudinal bias is seen in the IAPCAS data with respect to the model. The origin of these biases will be the subject of future work.

1.2 Mission Quality Assessment Matrix

Product Information		Product Generation		Ancillary Information		Uncertainty Characterisation		Validation	
Product Details	Sensor Calibration & Characterisation Pre-Flight	Product Flags		Uncertainty Characterisation Method		Reference Data Representativeness			
Availability & Accessibility	Sensor Calibration & Characterisation Post-Launch	Ancillary Data		Uncertainty Sources Included		Reference Data Quality			
Product Format	Retrieval Algorithm Method			Uncertainty Values Provided		Validation Method			
User Documentation	Retrieval Algorithm Tuning			Geolocation Uncertainty		Validation Results			
Metrological Traceability Documentation	Additional Processing								

Key	
Not Assessed	
Not Assessable	
Basic	
Intermediate	
Good	
Excellent	
Information Not Public	

Figure 1 – TanSat/ACGS Quality Evaluation Matrix.

2. MISSION ASSESSMENT OVERVIEW

2.1 Product Information

Product Details	
Product Name	TanSat L2 XCO ₂ and L2 SIF
Sensor Name	Atmospheric Carbon Dioxide Grating Spectrometer (ACGS)
Sensor Type	NIR/SWIR – Multichannel spectrometer
Mission Type	Single Satellite
Mission Orbit	Sun Synchronous
Product Version Number	v1.1 OCFP, v. 1.0 (XCO ₂) and TanSat Solar-Induced Chlorophyll Fluorescence Product, V1.0 (SIF)
Product ID	CO2_TAN_OCFP CO2_TAN_OCFP (XCO ₂) and ACGS_ND_V02 (SIF)
Processing level of product	Level 2
Measured Quantity Name	Column-averaged dry air mole fraction of CO ₂ (XCO ₂) and Solar Induced Fluorescence (SIF)
Measured Quantity Units	ppm (XCO ₂) and mW/m ² /sr/nm (SIF)
Stated Measurement Quality	Uncertainty provided for each retrieval; generally below 1.2 ppm (XCO ₂) and 0.1 mW/m ² /sr/nm (SIF)
Spatial Resolution	2x2km
Spatial Coverage	18km
Temporal Resolution	Daily
Temporal Coverage	16-day repeat cycle
Point of Contact	Dr Simon Preval, Dongxu Yang and Hartmut Boesch (XCO ₂); and Liangyun, Liu (liuly@radi.ac.cn) (SIF)
Product locator (DOI/URL)	http://dx.doi.org/10.5285/2cc63301f1854239aa61c70e58c61207 (XCO ₂) and https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3883434 (SIF)
Conditions for access and use	N/A
Limitations on public access	L2 UoL-FP product freely available. L2 IAPCAS product not yet available. XCO ₂ : Global data available for June 2017 and August 2017; data over selected TCCON stations for a time period of 2017-03-01 to 2018-05-22 SIF: Time period of 2017-03-01 to 2019-08-31 global data publicly available
Product Abstract	The University of Leicester Full-Physics Retrieval Algorithm (UoL-FP) is an optical estimation retrieval algorithm for TanSat. For the CO ₂ Full Physics product, it utilises the O ₂ -A absorption band along with the weak CO ₂ band located at 1.6 um respectively to retrieve XCO ₂ (the column-average dry-air mole fraction of atmospheric CO ₂). The explicit consideration of scattering by this approach reduces potential systematic biases due to clouds or aerosols.

	<p>XCO₂:</p> <p>This dataset contains column-average dry-air mole fractions of atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂), derived from the TANSAT satellite, using the University of Leicester Full-Physics Retrieval Algorithm (UoL-FP, also known as OCFP). This dataset is also referred to as CO₂_TAN_OCFP. The data covers the period from March 2017 to May 2018 and is provided for TCCON (Total Carbon Column Observing Network) validation sites only. A full global dataset is in production. For further information on the dataset, please see the linked documentation.</p> <p>This data has been produced as part of the European Space Agency (ESA)'s Climate Change Initiative (CCI) programme, with support from the UK's National Centre for Earth Observation (NCEO).</p> <p>SIF:</p> <p>The TanSat Solar Induce chlorophyll fluorescence (SIF) retrievals acquired from the ACGS spectroradiometer onboard TanSat make use of O2-A band L1 data with 0.044 nm spectral resolution and wavelengths between 757.4 and 778.1 nm.</p> <p>The TanSat SIF products contain effective SIF values (including SIF_758nm and SIF_771nm) and other geometric information (Latitude, longitude, angles and so forth). There is one file per day if the corresponding ACGS L1B data is available.</p>
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Availability & Accessibility	
Compliant with FAIR principles	Yes, for UoL-FP, No for IAPCAS
Data Management Plan	N/A
Availability Status	<p>L1 data available at: https://fy4.nsmc.org.cn/data/en/code/TANSAT.html#ACGS L2 UoL-FP data not yet available. L2 IAPCAS data not yet available.</p> <p>XCO₂: Global data available for June 2017 and August 2017; data over selected TCCON stations for a time period of 2017-03-01 to 2018-05-22 SIF: Data available for time period of 2017-03-01 to 2019-08-31</p>

Product Format	
Product File Format	netCDF4
Metadata Conventions	CCI Data Standards v2.2
Analysis Ready Data?	Yes (xco2_quality_flag = 0)

User Documentation		
Document	Reference	QA4ECV Compliant
Product User Guide	IAPCAS Product User Guide (PUG) not yet available. PUG v3 (CO2_TAN_OCFP v1.1) available for UoL-FP TanSat product from the ESA CCI+ project.	No
ATBD	IAPCAS Algorithm Theoretical Basis Document (ATBD) not yet available. ATBD available for UoL-FP TanSat product from the ESA CCI+ project.	No

Metrological Traceability Documentation	
Document Reference	N/A. Very few information provided.
Traceability Chain / Uncertainty Tree Diagram Available	No

2.2 Product Generation

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation – Pre-Flight	
Summary	Sensor calibration meets the satellite mission design requirement
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lin, C., Li, C., Wang, L., Bi, Y., & Zheng, Y. (2017), <i>Preflight spectral calibration of hyperspectral carbon dioxide spectrometer of TanSat (in Chinese)</i>, <i>Opt. Precis. Eng.</i> 25(8), 2064-2075 Wang, L., Lin, C., Ji, Z., Zheng, Y., & Bi, Y. (2018), <i>Preflight diffuser's calibration of carbon dioxide spectrometer of TanSat (in Chinese)</i>, <i>Opt. Precis. Eng.</i> 26(8), 1967-1976 Yang, Z., Zheng, Y., Yin, Z., et al. (2018), <i>Prelaunch Radiometric Calibration of the TanSat Atmospheric Carbon Dioxide Grating Spectrometer</i>, in <i>IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing</i>, vol 56, no 7, pp. 4225-4233 Yang, Z., Zhen, Y., Yin, Z., et al., (2018), <i>Laboratory spectral calibration of the TanSat Atmospheric Carbon dioxide Grating Spectrometer</i>, <i>Geosci. Instrum. Method. Data Syst.</i>, 7, 245-252

Sensor Calibration & Characterisation – Post-Launch	
Summary	On-orbit spectral calibration involves two parts that are the instrument line shape (ILS) calibration and wavelength calibration (based on a common diffuser used for solar observation): <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) Spectral calibration using individual solar lines 2) Calibration with entire atmospheric spectra.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> YANG Zhong-Dong, BI Yan-Meng, WANG Qi, Cheng-Bao Liu, XU Na, Lei Yang, Song-Yan Gu, Maiyun Lin, (March 2018, GCIS) <i>In-Flight Performance of TanSat Atmospheric Carbon Dioxide Grating Spectrometer</i>. YANG Zhongdong, BI Yan-Meng, Wang Qian, (June 2017, 13th IWGGMS), <i>Preliminary Assessment of TanSat Atmospheric Carbon Dioxide Grating Spectroradiometer on-orbit Performance</i>

Retrieval Algorithm Method	
Summary	The IAPCAS Retrieval Algorithm is a full-physics retrieval scheme developed by IAP, CAS using the Optimal Estimation Method. The University of Leicester Full-Physics (UoL-FP) algorithm is an Optimal Estimation Retrieval Algorithm.
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yang, D., Liu, Y., Cai, Z., Deng, J., Wang, J., & Chen, X. (2015), <i>An Advanced Carbon Dioxide Retrieval Algorithm for Satellite Measurements and its Application to GOSAT Observations</i>, <i>Chin. Sci. Bull.</i>, 60(23), 2063-2066. Yang, D., Liu, Y., Cai, Z., Chen, X., Yao, L., & Lu, D., (2018), <i>First Global Carbon Dioxide Maps Produced from TanSat Measurements</i>, <i>Adv. Atmos. Sci.</i>, 35, 621-623. Bösch, H., Toon, G. C., Sen, B., et al, (2006), <i>JGR</i>, 111, D23302

Retrieval Algorithm Tuning	
Summary	Fourier Series approach to improve radiometric calibration has been included in the L2 Retrieval.

References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Yang, D., Boesch, H., Liu, Y., et al., (2020), <i>Toward High Precision XCO₂ Retrievals from TanSat Observations: Retrieval Improvement and Validation against TCCON Measurements</i>, <i>JGR Atmospheres</i>, 125, 22, 2020JD032794
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Additional Processing	
Additional Processing	
Description	N/A
Reference	N/A

2.3 Ancillary Information

Product Flags	
Product Flag Documentation	xco2_quality_flags variable is included with the UoL-FP L2 product and is described in the UoL-FP PUGv3.
Comprehensiveness of Flags	N/A (the product does not include all features)

Ancillary Data	
Ancillary Data Documentation	N/A
Comprehensiveness of Data	N/A
Uncertainty Quantified	No

2.4 Uncertainty Characterisation

Uncertainty Characterisation Method	
Summary	The reported uncertainty for the UoL-FP retrieval has been tested against the observed scatter against ground-truth data from the TCCON.
Reference	End-to-End ECV Uncertainty Budget (E3UBv3) CO ₂ _TAN_OCFP v1.1 from the ESA CCI+ project.

Uncertainty Sources Included	
Summary	Info and details not available. One study has focused on optimising the aerosol model for the CO ₂ algorithm.
Reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Chen, X., Liu, Y., Yang, D., Cai, Z., Chen, H., Wang, M., <i>A Theoretical Analysis for Improving Aerosol-Induced CO₂ Retrieval Uncertainties Over Land Based on TanSat Nadir Observations Under Clear Sky Conditions</i>, <i>Remote Sens.</i>, 2019, 11, 1061

Uncertainty Values Provided	
Summary	Values for the a-posteriori uncertainty in XCO ₂ are provided in the L2 data products.
Reference	N/A
Analysis Ready Data?	No

Geolocation Uncertainty	
Summary	N/A
Reference	N/A

2.5 Validation

Validation Activity #1	
Independently Assessed?	Yes
<i>Reference Data Representativeness</i>	
Summary	TCCON ground based measurement
Reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wunch, D., Toon, G. C., Blavier, J.-F. L., Washenfelder, R. A., Notholt, J., Connor, B. J., Griffith, D. W. T., Sherlock, V., & Wennberg, P. O., (2011a), <i>The Total Carbon Column Observing Network</i>, <i>Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A</i>, 369, 2087-2112, doi:10.1098/rsta.2010.0240
<i>Reference Data Quality & Suitability</i>	
Summary	TCCON is a well-known validation standard for Greenhouse gas satellite measurements that has been used for GOSAT, OCO-2, TROMPOMI validation etc.
Reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wunch, D., Toon, G. C., Blavier, J.-F. L., Washenfelder, R. A., Notholt, J., Connor, B. J., Griffith, D. W. T., Sherlock, V., & Wennberg, P. O., (2011a), <i>The Total Carbon Column Observing Network</i>, <i>Phil. Trans. R. Soc. A</i>, 369, 2087-2112, doi:10.1098/rsta.2010.0240
<i>Validation Method</i>	
Summary	Tansat retrievals have been validated against TCCON globally (20 sites). A colocation criterion of $\pm 3^\circ$ in latitude/longitude and ± 1 h for matching up the TanSat soundings and TCCON measurements is applied.
Reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Wunch et al., (2017), <i>Comparisons of the Orbiting Carbon Observatory-2 (OCO-2) XCO₂ measurements with TCCON</i>, <i>Atmos. Meas. Tech.</i>, 10, 2209-2238, doi:10.5194/amt-10-2209-2017
<i>Validation Results</i>	
Summary	For bias-corrected UoL-FP retrievals an average XCO ₂ bias of -0.08ppm and an RMSE of 1.47ppm has been found by the data provider. Independent assessment against TCCON showed a mean bias of 0.04ppm and a relative accuracy (given by the standard deviation of biases per site) of 0.93 ppm. IAPCAS retrievals (without bias correction) show an RMSE of 1.53 ppm.

Reference	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• <i>Yang, D., Boesch, H., Liu, Y., et al., (2020), Toward High Precision XCO₂ Retrievals from TanSat Observations: Retrieval Improvement and Validation against TCCON Measurements, JGR Atmospheres, 125, 22, 2020JD032794</i>• <i>Product Validation and Inter-comparisons Report PVIRv1, ESA CCI+ Project</i>
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3. TANSAT DETAILED DATA ASSESSMENT

3.1 Comparisons between UoL-FP and IAPCAS

Since the release of the report EDAP.REP.21 global, land-only data has become available as retrieved by UoL-FP and IAPCAS. The methodology behind data filtering for UoL-FP has been detailed in Yang et al. (2020). A different filtering/quality control scheme has been used for the IAPCAS dataset. Retrievals where the XCO₂ uncertainty is greater than 2ppm, or where the sum of AOD type 1 and type 2 are greater than 0.3 are discarded. The UoL-FP dataset contains a factor of 2-3 more datapoints than the IAPCAS dataset. The looser filter applied to UoL-FP leads to increased coverage but might also lead to more outliers being included in the UoL-FP dataset. Therefore, all of the comparisons detailed in this document will use a truncated version of the UoL-FP dataset, where we use only soundings that occur in both the UoL-FP and the IAPCAS datasets unless otherwise stated.

3.1.1 Monthly Median Maps

In this section we compare the global median XCO₂ distributions for UoL-FP and IAPCAS spanning March 2017 to November 2017. In Figures Figure 2, Figure 3, and Figure 4 we show the global median bias-corrected XCO₂ as retrieved by UoL-FP and IAPCAS, and the arithmetic difference between them, ΔXCO₂, where $\Delta XCO_2 = (XCO_{2,UoL} - XCO_{2,IAPCAS})$, for March to May, June to August, and September to November respectively. The largest differences between the UoL-FP and IAPCAS retrievals can be seen in the tropical latitudes, where there are no TCCON stations available for bias correction.

Figure 2 – Global monthly median XCO₂ concentrations as a function of longitude/latitude from UoL-FP (left), IAPCAS (middle), and their arithmetic difference (right) for March 2017 – May 2017.

Figure 3 – Global monthly median XCO₂ concentrations as a function of longitude/latitude from UoL-FP (left), IAPCAS (middle), and their arithmetic difference (right) for June 2017 – August 2017.

Figure 4 – Global monthly median XCO₂ concentrations as a function of longitude/latitude from UoL-FP (left), IAPCAS (middle), and their arithmetic difference (right) for September 2017 – November 2017.

In Figure 5 we give histograms showing the distribution of ΔXCO_2 for March 2017 to November 2017, and also include box and whisker diagrams showing the distribution of the data and its outliers. The mean and median ΔXCO_2 values for all months are within 0.6 ppm of zero difference, and all standard deviations are < 2.0 ppm. The quoted RMSEs for UoL-FP and IAPCAS are 1.47 and 1.53 ppm respectively. Added in quadrature, the combined RMSE is 2.12 ppm. As the standard deviation of ΔXCO_2 for all months is < 2.0 ppm, this indicates the retrievals from UoL-FP and IAPCAS are in good agreement with each other within their uncertainty.

Figure 5 – Histogram of arithmetical differences between monthly-median values of XCO_2 as retrieved by UoL-FP and IAPCAS spanning months March 2017 to November 2017.

3.1.2 Latitudinal Averages

In this section we compare the latitudinal-averaged, bias-corrected XCO_2 as retrieved by UoL-FP and IAPCAS. In Figure 6, Figure 7, and Figure 8 we show March 2017 – May 2017, June 2017 – August 2017, and September 2017 – November 2017 respectively. We also include plots depicting the arithmetic difference between them. As was seen in Figures Figure 2, Figure 3, and Figure 4 the largest differences can be seen at tropical latitudes (0-20°N) for all months considered. These differences are particularly large for July, August, and September with differences spanning 3-4 ppm spanning latitudes of 0-40°N. The best agreement is seen at the highest and lowest latitudes with differences confined to <1 ppm. November appears to show better agreement than the other months, but this may be due to the reduced number of data points available for this month.

Figure 6 – Latitudinal average of TanSat bias corrected XCO₂ retrievals from the UoL-FP (blue) and IAPCAS (orange) algorithms (left plot), and the arithmetic difference between them (right plot) for March 2017 – May 2017. The horizontal-dashed line on the right plot indicates zero difference between the two algorithms.

Figure 7 – Latitudinal average of TanSat bias corrected XCO₂ retrievals from the UoL-FP (blue) and IAPCAS (orange) algorithms (left plot), and the arithmetic difference between them (right plot) for June 2017 – August 2017. The horizontal-dashed line on the right plot indicates zero difference between the two algorithms.

Figure 8 – Latitudinal average of TanSat bias corrected XCO₂ retrievals from the UoL-FP (blue) and IAPCAS (orange) algorithms (left plot), and the arithmetic difference between them (right plot) for September 2017 – November 2017. The horizontal-dashed line on the right plot indicates zero difference between the two algorithms.

3.1.3 Global Seasonal Average

In Figure 9, we plot the global seasonal cycle of bias-corrected XCO₂ for TanSat (UoL-FP and IAPCAS), GOSAT (UoL-FP), and OCO-2 (FOCAL). As we consider OCO-2 and GOSAT in this comparison, we do not match the exposure IDs in the UoL-FP and IAPCAS TanSat datasets. The general seasonal variation is reproduced by all four cycles. However, there are significant differences between all four cycles. The largest differences are confined to ~2-3 ppm, and appear to occur around May – June 2017/2018. These differences can occur for multiple reasons. For instance, the GOSAT/OCO-2 datasets will use different bias-correction methods and filtering. As the exposure IDs have not been matched, this will result in differences in the average XCO₂ calculated for the TanSat datasets.

Figure 9 – Global seasonal variation for TanSat as processed by UoL-FP (blue) and IAPCAS (red), GOSAT (orange) as processed by UoL-FP, and OCO-2 (green) as processed by FOCAL. A 30-day rolling average has been applied to the data.

3.1.4 Giorgi-region plots

In this section we compare the seasonal cycles from TanSat, OCO-2, and GOSAT for various regions from the Giorgi & Franciso (2008) paper. The authors created a map of regions over a map of the Earth delimited by the type of vegetation found in these regions. These regions are indicated in Figure 10.

Figure 10 – Giorgi & Franciso (2000) regions used to assess regional seasonal trends.

In Figure 11 we plot the XCO₂ seasonal pattern for the Giorgi regions (land-only) for TanSat (UoL-FP/IAPCAS), GOSAT (UoL-FP), and OCO-2 (FOCAL). For this comparison, we do not match the TanSat sounding IDs and opt to use all available, quality-filtered data. We applied a 30-day rolling average to the data to make the seasonal pattern clearer. In two-thirds of regions the regions considered all four trends are in good agreement with each other, with values differing by <1 ppm. Compare, for example, the seasonal trend for Northern Europe (NEU) in Figure 11. The TanSat UoL-FP and IAPCAS seasonal patterns follow each other closely in many regions with differences

of <1 ppm. This is easiest to see for Western North America (WNA). Notable regions where the agreement seems to differ (>2 ppm) are Alaska (ALA), the Amazon Basin (AMZ), Greenland (GRL), Sahara (SAH), Southeast Asia (SEA), South Asia (SAS), and Tibet (TIB). In most cases the disagreement arises from a lack of coverage.

Figure 11 – XCO₂ seasonal cycles as observed in the Giorgi regions for TanSat as retrieved by UoL-FP/IAPCAS (blue and red respectively), GOSAT (orange), and OCO-2 (green). A 30-day rolling average has been applied to smooth the data.

3.1.5 Global seasonal-average comparisons

In this section we compare the seasonal averages calculated from the UoL-FP and IAPCAS datasets. As before, we cross correlate the two datasets and use only soundings that exist in both datasets. In Figure 12, we plot the bias corrected, seasonally averaged XCO₂ as a function of longitude/latitude for UoL-FP, IAPCAS, and the arithmetic difference between them. We include plots for spring (March 2017 – May 2017), summer (June 2017 – August 2017) and autumn (September 2017 – November 2017). As with previous examples we can see that the largest differences occur at tropical latitudes. However, for the summer and autumn months for latitudes > 40° the UoL-FP seasonal average is larger than the IAPCAS seasonal average, whereas for lower latitudes the reverse is true.

Figure 12 – Seasonally averaged XCO₂ concentrations as a function of longitude/latitude for TanSat UoL-FP (left plots) and IAPCAS (middle plots), and the arithmetic difference between them (right plots).

3.2 Comparison between IAPCAS and UoL-FP TanSat retrievals and CAMS

In this section, we compare the TanSat retrievals from IAPCAS and UoL-FP to the CAMSft18r1 model. The inversion system used to generate the model is known as PyVar, and has been used in other projects such as GEMS, MACC, MACC-II, and MACC-III (see Chevallier 2018a for more information). The ft18r1 model utilises the general circulation model LMDZ (Locatelli et al. 2015) and the deep convection model of Emanuel (1991). The XCO₂ predictions are constrained using measurements collected within ObsPack (Masarie et al. 2014). This includes measurements from TCCON as well as from GOSAT and OCO-2. Therefore, comparisons to CAMSft18r1 not only provide a direct comparison to the underlying model, but also an indirect comparison to the satellites used in constructing CAMSft18r1. To perform our comparisons, we co-locate the TanSat measurements and the model predictions for each day. We then apply the TanSat averaging kernels from IAPCAS and UoL-FP to the model CO₂ profiles from CAMSft18r1. Next, for both IAPCAS and UoL-FP retrievals, and the model values we calculate the monthly median XCO₂ as a function of longitude and latitude and plot them on a global map. Lastly, we calculate the difference between the monthly median calculated for IAPCAS, UoL-FP, and CAMSft18r1 and plot a global map of these differences as a function of longitude and latitude. As with the previous comparisons, we only use exposure IDs that exist in both UoL-FP and IAPCAS.

3.2.1 IAPCAS vs CAMSFT18R1

In Figures Figure 13, Figure 14, and Figure 15, we plot the XCO₂ distributions for the IAPCAS TanSat retrievals (left plots), CAMSft18r1 (middle plots), and the arithmetic difference between them (right plots) for March 2017 – May 2017, June 2017 – August 2017, and September 2017 – November 2017 respectively.

Figure 13 – Comparison of the bias corrected global median XCO₂ distributions as a function of longitude/latitude for the IAPCAS TanSat retrievals (left plots), the CAMSf18r1 model (middle plots), and the arithmetic difference between them (right plots) for March 2017 – May 2017.

Figure 14 – Comparison of the bias corrected global median XCO₂ distributions as a function of longitude/latitude for the IAPCAS TanSat retrievals (left plots), the CAMSf18r1 model (middle plots), and the arithmetic difference between them (right plots) for June 2017 – August 2017.

Figure 15 – Comparison of the bias corrected global median XCO₂ distributions as a function of longitude/latitude for the IAPCAS TanSat retrievals (left plots), the CAMSf18r1 model (middle plots), and the arithmetic difference between them (right plots) for September 2017 – November 2017.

In Figure 16 we plot histograms showing the distribution of ΔXCO_2 for March 2017 – November 2017, where $\Delta XCO_2 = (XCO_{2,IAPCAS} - XCO_{2,camsf18r1})$, and also include box and whisker diagrams showing the distribution of data and outliers. In all cases the distribution of ΔXCO_2 is centred closely to the zero difference, or is within 1 ppm of the zero difference. The best agreement with the CAMS model occurs for June 2017 and September 2017 with median differences of -0.04 and -0.001 ppm respectively. The spread of ΔXCO_2 when comparing IAPCAS to CAMSf18r1 is also relatively small with the standard deviation of ΔXCO_2 for all months < 2.0 ppm. The standard deviations of ΔXCO_2 for the IAPCAS model comparisons are not dissimilar to those observed when considering ΔXCO_2 between the UoL-FP and IAPCAS retrievals. For instance, the standard deviation of ΔXCO_2 for June 2017 and September 2017 is 1.685 and 1.506 ppm respectively when comparing UoL-FP and IAPCAS, whereas the standard deviations are 1.454 and 1.541 ppm respectively when comparing to CAMSf18r1. If we regard the ΔXCO_2 distribution for UoL-FP and IAPCAS as an indicator of precision, then the ΔXCO_2 distribution for IAPCAS and CAMSf18r1 indicates that the IAPCAS retrievals are in good agreement with the model. For the majority of the ΔXCO_2 distributions a double peak (positive/negative difference) is discernible. This is most easily seen for July 2017. The reason for this can be seen when considering the longitude/latitude plots in Figures Figure 13, Figure 14, and Figure 15. For all months we can see that the IAPCAS retrievals are smaller than the model at

high latitudes, and larger than the model at lower latitudes. This indicates the presence of a latitudinal bias in the IAPCAS dataset.

Figure 16 – Histograms depicting the arithmetic difference between monthly median retrieved IAPCAS XCO₂ values and the CAMSf18r1 model XCO₂ values for March 2017 – November 2017.

3.2.2 UoL-FP vs CAMSFT18R1

The comparison between UoL-FP and CAMSf18r1 was performed as an additional check for data quality with the other three objectives described in the executive summary. Unlike the other comparisons described previously, we have not matched the exposure IDs in the UoL-FP dataset with IAPCAS. Instead, the only filters applied to the UoL-FP dataset are those described in Yang et al. (2020). Given that we have already observed good agreement between UoL-FP and IAPCAS when only soundings common to both datasets are used, this exercise provides an important check on the impact of using different filters on model agreement. In Figure 17, Figure 18, and Figure 19 we have plotted the global monthly medians for UoL-FP, the CAMSf18r1 model, and the arithmetic difference between them for March 2017 – May 2017, June 2017 – August 2017, and September 2017 – November 2017 respectively.

Figure 17 – Comparison of the bias corrected global median XCO₂ distributions as a function of longitude/latitude for the UoL-FP TanSat retrievals (left plots), the CAMSf18r1 model (middle plots), and the arithmetic difference between them (right plots) for March 2017 – May 2017.

Figure 18 – Comparison of the bias corrected global median XCO₂ distributions as a function of longitude/latitude for the UoL-FP TanSat retrievals (left plots), the CAMSf18r1 model (middle plots), and the arithmetic difference between them (right plots) for June 2017 – August 2017.

Figure 19 – Comparison of the bias corrected global median XCO₂ distributions as a function of longitude/latitude for the UoL-FP TanSat retrievals (left plots), the CAMSf18r1 model (middle plots), and the arithmetic difference between them (right plots) for September 2017 – November 2017.

In Figure 20 we plot histograms showing the distribution of ΔXCO_2 for March 2017 – November 2017, where $\Delta XCO_2 = (XCO_{2,UoL-FP} - XCO_{2,camsf18r1})$, and also include box and whisker diagrams showing the distribution of data and outliers. As with the IAPCAS dataset the standard deviations of ΔXCO_2 for UoL-FP and CAMSf18r1 are not dissimilar to those observed when comparing ΔXCO_2 for UoL-FP and IAPCAS. Again, if we regard the UoL and IAPCAS ΔXCO_2 distribution as an indicator of precision, then we can say the UoL-FP retrievals are in good agreement with CAMSf18r1. However, we note that generally the standard deviation of ΔXCO_2 for UoL-FP and CAMSf18r1 are larger than that of IAPCAS and CAMSf18r1. The standard deviations of ΔXCO_2 values for March – May and September – November are all < 2.0 ppm, whereas for June – August 2017 the standard deviation is > 2.0ppm. It can also be seen that the mean and median values of ΔXCO_2 for June and July 2017 are ~1.5 ppm. The mean/median values of May 2017 are ~1.0 ppm, whereas the remaining months are comparatively much smaller ranging from 0.1 – 0.5 ppm. This indicates that there is an additional seasonal bias present in the UoL-FP dataset that needs to be addressed. This could be a function of the retrieval algorithm or could be a result of something unaccounted for in the CAMSf18r1 model. The double peak structure observed in the IAPCAS/CAMSf18r1 ΔXCO_2 distributions does not appear to be present in the UoL-FP/CAMSf18r1 ΔXCO_2 distributions.

Figure 20 – Histograms depicting the arithmetic difference between monthly median retrieved IAPCAS XCO₂ values and the CAMSft18r1 model XCO₂ values for March 2017 – November 2017.

3.3 XCO₂ Accuracy and Precision Against TCCON

TanSat OCFP Level 2 XCO₂ product was evaluated against 21 ground-based FTS instruments that participate in the Total Carbon Column Observing Network (TCCON; Wunch et al., 2011; Figure 21). The spatiotemporal co-location criteria for the evaluation were same-day soundings within 2.5 degrees in latitude and 5.0 degrees in longitude, which have been applied also in other similar assessments (e.g., Boesch et al., 2021; Taylor et al., 2021). We present an evaluation of the daily mean values which mostly correspond to overpass-averaged statistics.

Figure 21: The Total Carbon Column Observing Network of ground-based Fourier Transform Spectrometers used in the evaluation of TanSat XCO₂ data. From: tccondata.org.

The biases for daily-averaged TanSat OCFP XCO₂ against 21 ground-based FTS as well as the standard deviations are listed in Table 1 and also presented in Figure 22. Relative biases at all sites are smaller than or equal to 0.71%. The magnitude of the bias varies between the sites, and the largest bias of -2.9 ppm is obtained at Paris, corresponding to about -0.71%. Standard deviations of the bias vary mostly between 0.5–2.5 ppm, with an outlier of 7.0 ppm for Paris. Figure 22 shows that the bias is not globally systematic or latitudinally dependent but varies among the evaluation sites and FTS instruments.

In addition to the evaluation of the bias, i.e., the average difference in daily-averaged TanSat XCO₂ – TCCON XCO₂, the seasonal cycle amplitude and the growth rate were evaluated at all sites using nonlinear time series fitting (see Lindqvist et al., 2015, for methodological details). The time series comparisons as well as the fitted functions for the estimation of the growth rate and the seasonal cycle amplitude are presented in the panels of Figure 23. Due to the shortness of the co-located time series (less than two years), the fitting procedure may not reliably disentangle the growth rate and the amplitude; therefore, only those results where the fitting was technically successful, are shown in Figure 23. The seasonal cycle amplitude (in ppm) and the growth rate (slope in ppm/year) are estimated for each FTS comparison, along with statistical error estimates.

The growth rate is systematically higher for the TanSat OCFP than the TCCON, to the extent that a temporal drift may be possible. However, due to the short time series, which is reflected in the high uncertainties (see Figure 23, middle panel text), a reliable estimate on the longer-term stability of the product cannot be given.

The XCO₂ seasonal cycle amplitude depends on the geographical location: in the Southern hemisphere (SH), the seasonal variability in XCO₂ is small, resulting in a shallow seasonal cycle amplitude, generally less than 2 ppm. Due to the limited dataset, the SH seasonal cycle has only been evaluated at Lauder (see Figure 23), where a bias of 1.39 ppm exceeds potential seasonal

biases in magnitude. In the Northern hemisphere, the TanSat seasonal cycle amplitude does not generally agree with the TCCON. However, this is to some extent likely due to the short time series. The largest differences are seen towards increasing latitudes (e.g., Sodankylä, East Trout Lake) where the seasonal coverage of observations is limited mostly due to the high solar zenith angles in winter. Otherwise, the agreement varies between the sites non-systematically, indicating that the data are not subject to large-scale seasonal biases (at least comparable to the magnitude of the XCO₂ seasonal variability).

Table 1. Evaluation of TANSAT XCO₂ against XCO₂ of ground-based Fourier Transform Spectrometers in the Total Carbon Column Observing Network (TCCON) sites, using the GGG2014 retrieval. The table shows the mean bias (TANSAT – TCCON; in ppm), the relative bias (in %) and the standard deviation (STD; in ppm) at a given site.

TCCON site	Bias	Rel. b. %	STD	TCCON site	Bias	Rel. b. %	STD
Bialystok	0.5	0.12	2.0	Lauder	1.4	0.34	1.3
Bremen	0.4	0.10	1.0	Orleans	1.2	0.29	1.1
Burgos	0.0	0.00	1.3	Paris	-2.9	-0.71	7.0
Caltech	-1.4	-0.34	1.8	Park Falls	0.0	0.00	1.5
Darwin	-0.2	-0.06	1.7	Rikubetsu	-1.6	-0.39	2.5
East Trout Lake	0.1	0.00	1.2	Saga	-1.2	-0.29	1.5
Edwards	1.1	0.27	0.5	Sodankylä	-0.2	-0.05	2.5
Garmisch	-0.2	-0.04	1.1	Tsukuba	-0.2	-0.05	2.3
JPL	-1.0	-0.24	2.1	Wollongong	-0.4	-0.09	1.2
Karlsruhe	0.9	0.21	1.9	Zugspitze	0.2	0.05	1.6
Lamont	0.6	0.15	1.3				

Figure 22. The accuracy and precision of TANSAT XCO₂ at the TCCON sites, presented as the mean of TANSAT – TCCON daily-averaged XCO₂. The error bars denote the standard deviation (in ppm). The evaluation sites are organised according to their latitude.

Bialystok

Bialystok

Sodankylä

Sodankylä

Figure 23. Sequence of four plots for each TCCON station: 1) correlation plot; 2) scatter plot over the time; 3) TANSAT vs TCCON daily median and fit over the time; 4) TANSAT vs TCCON daily median and fit over the time with fit parametrization.

3.3.1 Evaluation Of CO₂ Over Snow

At high latitudes, the most significant factor limiting the seasonal coverage of the passive satellite observations is the availability of solar radiation. Another challenge at high latitudes is snow-covered surfaces which absorb strongly in the near-infrared wavelengths, and which have not previously been separately evaluated. To study the TanSat XCO₂ retrieval performance over snow, we used NOAA's (U.S. National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration) IMS (Interactive Multisensor Snow and Ice Mapping System) Daily Northern Hemisphere Snow and Ice Analysis data set in 24 km resolution (U.S. National Ice Center, 2008). IMS data are a combination on various data products, for example, satellite and in situ data. We classified all TanSat observations based on IMS data and defined if they are made over snow, land, sea, or sea ice.

Figure 24 shows the time series of TanSat OCFP XCO₂ observations over 40°N for 2017–2018. The colours indicate the IMS classifications. As the publicly available TanSat OCFP data set shows observations only in the proximity of selected validation sites, the spatial distribution of the observations does not describe the true observation pattern of TanSat. In addition, there has been some breaks in the satellite operations during this observation period. Therefore, a thorough analysis on the coverage cannot be performed based on Figure 24. The absolute number of observations was the highest in March 2018, and the partition of snow-covered observations was also highest in March 2018 (Boesch et al., 2021). Based on this, it can be assumed that during

March there is already enough solar light northwards from 40°N to be able to make GHG satellite observations but which may be limited by the absorption of snow on the ground.

Figure 25 shows the statistical uncertainty of TanSat OCFP XCO₂ observations northwards from 40°N for observations over snow-free land and over snow. The mean statistical uncertainty for over snow-free land observations was 1.37 ppm and for over snow observations 3.11 ppm. The spread of the statistical uncertainty of observations over snow is also higher. This is partly due to the limited time series but also indicates that the uncertainty is generally larger for observations over snow than for snow-free landscape. The reasons for the higher statistical uncertainty for observations over snow should be studied in more detail in the future. An initial joint evaluation of the snow cover and solar zenith angle effects on the TanSat biases was carried out by the FMI team but remained largely inconclusive due to the limited amount of data. In addition, the retrieval uncertainty is affected by the different albedos over snow and land.

Figure 24. Time series of number of TANSAT XCO₂ observations over 40°N. Colours shows the snow and sea states at the ground on the observation point.

Figure 25. TANSAT XCO₂ statistical uncertainty for observations over 40°N, light brown shows the error for over snow observations and dark brown for over land observations

3.3.2 Assessment Of Prior Profiles Against Aircore Soundings

FMI has performed regular AirCore profile soundings (Karion et al., 2010) of greenhouse gases, for example, CO₂ and CH₄, at Sodankylä, Northern Finland, since 2013. These measurements provide a cost-efficient method for evaluating the shapes of the prior profiles used in the satellite retrievals.

Figure 26 shows all measured AirCore profiles for which there were co-located TanSat observations from within ± 2 days and within $\pm 5^\circ$ from the Sodankylä TCCON site. TanSat prior profiles agree very well with the AirCore profiles. The largest differences are found in the upper atmosphere during spring soundings. The autumn soundings capture the upper atmosphere well, but some differences remain near the surface. However, the agreement is significantly better for the TanSat retrieval prior profiles compared to the TCCON GGG2014 profiles. The latter show considerable discrepancies compared to the AirCore profiles, but this will hopefully improve with the updated TCCON GGG2020 retrieval that is expected to be published in early 2022.

Figure 26. TanSat prior (cyan) and TCCON GGG2014 (red) CO₂ prior profiles evaluated against measured AirCore (black) profiles at Sodankylä TCCON site for 2017 and 2018.

3.3.3 SIF evaluation in Northern Finland

TanSat Level 2 retrieval includes the retrieval of Solar-Induced Fluorescence (SIF), which is an indicator of photosynthetic activity of vegetation and has been found to systematically correlate with the ecosystem’s gross primary productivity (GPP), making it an important variable to detect from space. TanSat provides SIF as one of their official Level 2 products. Being a new product, it is important to evaluate this product. Here, we perform an evaluation of this product over Northern Finland (mostly evergreen needleleaf forest vegetation) as an example of the quality of the product at high latitudes. It should be noted that the validation of SIF is not yet well-established and therefore not straightforward. There are no established ground-truth networks for SIF, and the ground-level or tower-level measurements do not share the same footprint with the satellite. To evaluate the measurement quality, we have compared two satellite products against each other.

Figure 27 shows the SIF observations from Sentinel-5P TROPOMI TROPOSIF v2.0 product (Guanter et al., 2021) and TanSat (Du et al., 2018). The retrievals are made at different wavelengths, so we do not expect them to exactly agree as SIF is a spectrally-dependent signal. However, we would expect the photosynthetically active season to start, peak and end at the same time in both time series.

Both satellite products show a clear seasonal pattern. The patterns agree with each other well through the summer and autumn. In spring, however, there are disagreements on when the photosynthetically active season starts. Currently, the reason for this difference is not known, and we do not yet have ground-truth to evaluate which satellite is closer to the true SIF signal and its temporal variability. Still, the discrepancy discovered highlights the importance of establishing a ground-based, systematic validation network for SIF observations.

Figure 27. Daily average time series of Solar-Induced Fluorescence (SIF) from two satellite instruments: TROPOMI (green diamond) and TanSat (purple triangle).

4. CONCLUSIONS

We have presented a detailed intercomparison between TanSat retrievals processed by the UoL-FP and IAPCAS algorithms. We have compared global monthly medians, latitudinal averages, and seasonal average maps of bias corrected XCO₂ concentrations for these retrieval algorithms. We have also compared regional and global averaged seasonal cycles. For all global maps considered (see Figure 2 Figure 3 Figure 4) it can be seen that small differences exist between the UoL-FP and IAPCAS retrieved XCO₂ values. However, the largest differences can be seen at tropical latitudes. This can also be seen in the latitudinal averages.

In addition, we have assessed the performance of the UoL-FP and IAPCAS algorithms by using the CAMSft18r1 model as a truth proxy. The ft18r1 model was chosen due to its use of ObsPack to constrain the flux inversions performed in its construction. ObsPack includes observational data from OCO-2 and TCCON, further constraining the flux inversions and improving its accuracy. We noted that the spread of the Δ XCO₂ distribution for UoL-FP and CAMSft18r1 and IAPCAS and CAMSft18r1 were similar to that observed for the Δ XCO₂ distribution for UoL-FP/IAPCAS, indicating that the model agreed well with the retrieved UoL-FP and IAPCAS XCO₂.

We found that the Δ XCO₂ distributions when comparing IAPCAS and CAMSft18r1 showed a double peak (positive/negative differences). When viewed in the context of Δ XCO₂ as a function of longitude/latitude, a latitudinal bias in the IAPCAS dataset appears to be present. Generally, the standard deviation of Δ XCO₂ for UoL-FP and CAMSft18r1 was larger than that of IAPCAS/CAMSft18r1. When comparing UoL-FP and CAMSft18r1 the standard deviation of Δ XCO₂ was seen to be largest for June and July 2017, indicating the UoL-FP dataset has a seasonal bias.

Overall, the exposure ID matched TanSat retrievals as processed by UoL-FP are in good agreement with the retrievals from those processed by IAPCAS. Good agreement is also seen between the model predictions from CAMSft18r1 and UoL-FP and IAPCAS. The consistency between UoL-FP, IAPCAS, and the model calculations shows that the algorithms assessed in this report are robust and provide reliable retrievals of XCO₂. This is further reinforced by the fact that the CAMSft18r1 model is constrained by OCO-2 and provides an indirect benchmark for observations from TanSat.

In comparison to the TCCON measurements, station-specific TanSat OCFP v1.0 XCO₂ biases were between -1.6 ppm–1.4 ppm and standard deviations below 2.5 ppm, except for Paris TCCON site, where the bias and standard deviation were larger as driven by few anomalous retrieval values. This accuracy and precision may be sufficient to reduce CO₂ flux uncertainties in inverse modelling (e.g., Miller et al., 2007) but not sufficient for anthropogenic emission estimation (evaluated based on GCOS ECV requirements). The biases were random and there was no noticeable geographical dependence. The growth rate and seasonal cycle amplitude were analysed for TanSat and TCCON XCO₂ products. The limited length of the co-located time series affects the results as the growth rate cannot be reliably disentangled from the seasonal variability. The growth rate is found to be systematically higher for the TanSat OCFP than the TCCON, to the extent that a temporal drift may be possible. However, due to the short time series, a reliable estimate on the longer-term stability of the product cannot be given. The XCO₂ seasonal cycle amplitude for TanSat does not generally agree with the TCCON. However, this is likely due to the short time series. High-latitude stations with a limited seasonal coverage had the highest uncertainties in the seasonal cycle amplitude.

In the high-latitude specific evaluation, the seasonal coverage of TanSat observations was assessed, and the snow-covered footprints were identified. TanSat mission does provide retrievals over snow, albeit their amount is not large. The retrieval errors are systematically higher for observations over snow compared to observations over snow-free landscape.

The prior profiles of TanSat OCFP and TCCON GGG2014 retrieval algorithms were evaluated against balloon AirCore profile measurements of CO₂ at Sodankylä, Northern Finland, between 2017–2018. A very good agreement between the TanSat prior profile shapes and the AirCore

measurements is found. The largest deviations from the AirCore profiles occurred in spring at upper troposphere and lower stratosphere.

An initial evaluation of the TanSat Level 2 SIF v1.0 product was carried out in Northern Finland by comparing to Sentinel-5P TROPOMI TROPOSIF v2.0 SIF product due to the absence of established ground-based networks. TanSat SIF product showed a good agreement on the timing of the peak photosynthesis and end-of-season with the TROPOSIF. During spring, a disagreement was found between TanSat and S-5P SIF. The reason for the discrepancy was not yet identified; it provides an example on the emerging need to provide reliable ground-based validation data for SIF, in addition to greenhouse gases.

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